

The Lunar Electromagnetic Monitor in X-rays: concept, design and instrument development.

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Context: The surface of the Moon is an interesting and promising platform for an all-sky X-ray observatory. The scientific goal is a continuous observation in search of transients and interesting events in the context of Multi-Messenger Astrophysics [1]. The all-sky coverage can be obtained by exploiting the rotation of the Moon itself. The new interest for the Moon exploration and infrastructures offers great opportunities for this purpose.

Description of the project: The Lunar Electromagnetic Monitor in X-rays (LEM-X) is an all-sky X-ray observatory proposed for the surface of the Moon. The building block of LEM-X is a pair of coded aperture cameras, able to image the sky in a field of view of ~ 2 sr (at zero response) with a source location accuracy of ~ 1 arcmin. The LEM-X instrument envisages five of such camera pairs, arranged on a dome-shaped structure, to reach a sensitivity better than 1 Crab for short transients (1 s observation) and 5 mCrab for longer observations (50 ks observation) in the 2 – 50 keV energy band, with a spectral resolution better than 350 eV FWHM at 6 keV.

We are developing the engineering model of the LEM-X detection system [2] and studying the configuration of LEM-X for the Moon [3]. In particular, each detection system is composed of a linear Silicon Drift Detector connected via wire bondings to two rows of 11 custom developed ASICs [4], all integrated on a ceramic front-end board. Laboratory tests on a reduced scale but representative breadboard of this assembly show an adequate capability of reconstructing the position of the photon interaction on the detector, together with an energy resolution of ~ 160 eV at 5.9 keV for single-anode events at a temperature of -20 °C.

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Here we give an update of the LEM-X status, describe the instrument design and show the measured scientific performance of the prototypes.

References:

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